

Spectrophotometric determination of cadmium(II) and lead(II) using 5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione bithiosemicarbazone monohydrochloride

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Abstract : The reagent, 5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione bithiosemicarbazone monohydrochloride (5,5-DiMe-1,3-CHDT.HCl) gives orange red coloured complexes with cadmium(II) and lead(II) in ammonium chloride-ammonium hydroxide buffer medium. The molar absorptivities of cadmium and lead complexes respectively are 2.5×10^4 and 1.52×10^4 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. These color reactions have been investigated to develop spectrophotometric methods for the determination of cadmium(II) and lead(II) in aqueous medium. The reagent is used for the determination of cadmium in biological samples.

Keywords : Thiosemicarbazone, cadmium(II), lead(II).

Thiosemicarbazones are interesting analytical reagents. Although monothiosemicarbazones have been widely used for the spectrophotometric determination of metal ions, dithiosemicarbazones are not exploited much. In continuation of our on going work on the analytical application of substituted thiosemicarbazones¹, we report here the spectrophotometric determination of cadmium(II) and lead(II) using 5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione dithiosemicarbazone monohydrochloride (5,5-DiMe-1,3-CHDT.HCl).

Results and discussion

The reagent, 5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexanedione dithiosemicarbazone monohydrochloride (5,5-DiMe-1,3-CHDT.HCl) is easily prepared by simple condensation of 1 mol of dimedone with 2 mol of thiosemicarbazide. A 0.01 M solution of the reagent is stable for at least 12 h¹.

In basic medium, the ligand presumably exists in enolic form and coordinates the divalent metal ions as dianion. The reagent gives intense color reaction with cadmium(II) and lead(II) and show maximum absorbance at 430 and 435 nm respectively. The reagent is considered as potential for the sensitive spectrophotometric determination of cadmium(II) in aqueous samples.

Determination of cadmium(II) and lead(II) :

Cadmium(II) and lead(II) reacts with 5,5-DiMe-1,3-CHDT.HCl in basic medium to give orange red coloured complexes. The order of addition of reagent, metal ion (Cd²⁺ or Pb²⁺), buffer has no effect on the absorbance of the

complexes provided DMF is added prior to the addition of reagent solution. The absorbance of orange red coloured solutions remains constant for 40 min. A 30-fold molar excess of reagent is adequate for full color development. Addition of excess of reagent has no adverse effect on the absorbance of the complexes. The system obeys Beer's law in the concentration range 0.17–3.23, 0.33–5.96 µg ml⁻¹ of cadmium and lead respectively. The optimum ranges for the determination of cadmium and lead from Ringbom's plots are found to be 0.33–3.05, 0.45–4.75 µg ml⁻¹. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the methods for cadmium and lead are found to be 2.5×10^4 and 1.5×10^4 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0045 and 0.0136 µg cm⁻² respectively. The specific absorptivity of the methods are 0.073 and 0.222 ml g⁻¹ cm⁻¹ for the determination of cadmium and lead respectively.

Job's and molar ratio methods gave the composition of Cd and Pb complexes as 1 : 1 (M : L). The stability of the complexes of cadmium and lead complexes as calculated by Job's method are found to be 6.7×10^5 and 9.1×10^5 respectively.

The effect of foreign ions which often accompany cadmium and lead has been studied by adding different amounts of anions and cations to 0.45 and 2.07 µg ml⁻¹ (ppm) of cadmium and lead in solution respectively. The color is developed as described in the recommended procedure. An error of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance reading is considered tolerable. Common anions such as fluoride, chloride,

Note

bromide, iodide, nitrate, sulphate, thiosulphate, citrate tartrate and oxalate do not interfere in the determination of cadmium and lead when they are present in hundred fold molar excess. Metal ions such as vanadium(v), chromium(III), chromium(vi), manganese(II), iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), zinc(II), zirconium(IV), molybdenum(vi), tungsten(vi) and mercury(II) do not interfere when they are present in equal amounts.

Applications Cadmium was determined in different biological samples, viz. radish flesh, cabbage and cigarette tobacco.

Experimental

Schimidzu 160 A microcomputer based UV visible spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0 cm quartz cells was used for all absorbance measurements. An Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used for pH adjustments. All reagents used were of A.R. grade unless otherwise stated. All solutions were prepared with doubly distilled water. Stock solutions (0.01 M) cadmium(II) and lead(II) were prepared by dissolving requisite quantity of cadmium sulphate and lead nitrate in 250 ml distilled water respectively. The stock solutions were standardized and suitably diluted to obtain standard working solutions of metal ions.

The reagent is characterized by IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data*. The pK_a values were determined by recording the UV-visible spectra of micro molar (4 × 10⁻⁵ M) solution

of reagent at various pH values. Protonation constants of the reagent are pK₁ 6.5, pK₂ 9.3.

The reagent solution (0.01 M) was prepared by dissolving 325 mg of the compound in 100 ml of dimethylformamide and is stable for at least 12 h. Hydrochloric acid (1 M), sodium acetate (1 M) (pH 0.5–3.5), 0.2 M NaOAc-0.2 M AcOH (pH 4.0–6.5) and 2 M NH₄Cl-2 M NH₄OH buffer solutions were used in the present study.

Recommended procedures for the determination of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II}

Samples were prepared in 25 ml standard flasks with 10 ml of buffer (pH 10.25), metal ion (Cd, 0.33–5.96, Pb, 0.36–2.88 µg/ml), 2.5 ml of dimethylformamide and 1 ml of 0.01 M 5,5-DiMe-1,3-CHDT HCl and diluted to the volume with distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 430 nm for Cd, 435 nm for Pb, against a reagent blank as reference. The amounts of Cd and Pb were determined using respective calibration graphs.

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References

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